

The contribution of groundwater to total ET was maximum when plants were irrigated at 25% available soil moisture depletion at 0-30 cm depth. In drier regimes, the rice plant failed to extract moisture from the groundwater table, although the gradient of water potential was maximum. Liquid phase continuity was disturbed under the drier soil regimes, reducing groundwater contribution to a minimum. ■

Response of rice varieties to nitrogen manuring at Tirur, India

S. Nazeer Peeran and B. V. Anandam, Soil Science Section, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur 602025, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu, India

A field trial during *sornavari* 1980 (May-June to August-September) stu-

Grain yields (t/ha) of 6 rices treated with 5 nitrogen levels at Tirur, India.

Varieties	Grain yield (t/ha)					Mean	Fertilizer index
	No N	40kg N/ha	80 kg N/ha	120kg N/ha	160 kg N/ha		
AS1374	3.1	3.9	4.4	5.5 ^a	4.9	4.3	1.3
TM3207	2.8	3.4	4.0	4.3	4.7 ^a	3.8	1.2
TM2871	2.9	3.8	3.8	4.4	5.0 ^a	4.0	1.3
TM2048	2.8	3.2	3.8	4.1	4.3 ^a	3.1	1.2
TM1898	3.2	3.8	4.8	5.0	5.6 ^a	4.5	1.3
TKM9	3.6	4.0	5.0	5.6 ^a	5.5	4.7	1.2
Mean	3.1	3.7	4.3	4.8	5.0		
				F-test	SE	CD	
Variety				S**	0.095	0.541	
N levels				S**	0.053	0.345	
Interactions:							
				N level × variety	S**	0.088	0.347
				Variety × N level	S**	0.103	0.561

^a Highest optimum yields. **Significant at 0.99 level.

died the yield potential of pre-release cultures under different levels of nitrogen fertilizer (N). Six rice varieties and five N levels were tested in a split-plot design replicated twice (see table).

Yield differences were statistically significant for the interaction of nitrogen levels and rice varieties. TKM9 had the highest yield at all N levels of treatment, but had low response to N. ■

Contribution of seedling quality to rice production

S. A. Sattar, Harun-Ar-Rashid, and A. J. M. A. Islam, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI)

The contribution of seedling quality to grain yield and growth duration of transplanted rice was studied in the cold, dry, and wet seasons. High quality seedlings were produced by giving better management in the nursery; poor qual-

ity ones were obtained from a poorly managed nursery. A physical seedling quality index (SQI) was calculated (Table 1) and used for correlation analysis with yield, growth duration, and seedling strength measured in milligrams of dry matter produced per centimeter length of seedling.

The SQI correlated strongly with seedling strength (Table 2). SQ had no influence on grain yield and was negatively associated with growth duration. But high quality seedlings shortened crop growth duration by at least 6-10 days. ■

Table 1. Sample calculation of the physical quality index for rice seedlings, BRRI.

Seedling ht (cm)	Seedling ^a color rate (A)	Seedling strength (mg dry matter/cm) (B)	Seedling quality	
			(A) (B)	Index
11.1	5	8.97	44.9	100
11.1	5	7.57	37.8	84
10.1	4	5.51	22.0	49
10.3	4	4.11	16.4	36
9.2	2	6.33	12.7	28
8.9	2	4.20	8.4	18
9.0	1	3.50	3.5	8
9.8	1	2.65	2.55	6

^a 5-1 : deep green - yellow.

Table 2. Relationships among seedling quality and grain yield, growth duration, and seedling strength. BRRI.

Season	Variety	Correlation coefficient ^a		
		Yield	Growth duration (days)	Seedling strength
Boro, 1980	BR3	-.522	-.727*	.927**
	BR7	-.006	-.233	.965**
Boro, 1981	BR3	.678	-.838**	.901**
	BR9	.376	-.834**	.963**
Aus, 1981	BR3	.439	-.305	.894**
Aman, 1981	BR4	.529	-.845**	.990**

^a *significant at .05 level; **significant at .01 level.

Effect of planting time and density on yields of short-duration rice varieties

R. C. Gautam and K. C. Sharma, Agronomy Department, College of Agriculture, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, U.P., India

Field experiments during the kharif (wet) season 1975-77 at the Crop Research Centre (29° N lat, 79.3 E long, 243.84 m altitude) explored the effect of

planting density and planting time on yields of short-duration rice varieties.

Ratna, Rasi, and Cauvery were evaluated under two planting schemes:

a) 10 June sowing for all varieties and b) sowing on 20 June for Ratna, 5 July for Rasi, and 10 July for Cauvery. Jaya, a medium-duration high yielding variety, was planted 10 June as a check. Three planting densities, 400, 100, and 25 hills/m², were tested.

The short-duration varieties planted later responded better to high planting density (see table). Grain yields in high planting density (400 hills/m²) increased over normal planting density (25 hills/m²) by 10% in Ratna, 14% in Rasi, and 24% in Cauvery. These yields were compared with yields of medium-duration Jaya at normal planting density 2 of the 3 years of test. In 1976, a

Effect of time of planting and plant density on average^a grain yield of rice differing in growth duration in Pantnagar, India.

Variety and planting date	Grain yield (t/ha) at plant density			Mean (t/ha)
	400 hills/m ²	100 hills/m ²	25 hills/m ²	
Jaya 10 June	6.7	7.3	7.2	7.08
Ratna 10 June	6.8	6.7	6.5	6.64
Rasi 10 June	6.2	6.0	5.7	5.98
Cauvery 10 June	5.8	5.5	5.0	5.43
Ratna 20 June	6.9	6.6	6.2	6.57
Rasi 5 July	6.8	6.3	6.0	6.36
Cauvery 10 July	6.2	5.6	5.0	5.57
Mean	6.5	6.3	6.0	-

Treatment	S.E.m. +	C.D. (P = 0.05)
Planting time	0.12	0.37
Plant density	0.04	0.11
Plant density at same planting time	0.10	0.29
Planting time at same or different plant density	0.14	0.44

^aMean of 3 years.

thunderstorm during ripening caused severe damage to the short-duration varieties at high planting density. The higher yields of short-duration varieties

were ascribed to calm, cool, sunny weather during reproductive and ripening phases. ■

Efficiency of green manure substituted for applied nitrogen in rice

C. S. Khind, O. P. Meelu, and Viraj Beri, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana, India

Green manure crops were grown in 1979-81 to study their contribution to the nitrogen needs of a following rice crop.

Dhaincha, cowpea, and guara were sown in early May. The 2-month-old green-manure crops were buried 1 day before transplanting 45-day-old rice seedlings in early July.

Green matter, dry matter, and nitrogen added by guara was less than that added by dhaincha and cowpea (see table). Dhaincha and cowpea saved 90 kg N/ha, guara saved 60 kg N/ha (see figure).

The combined use of 60 kg N/ha applied as urea and green manure gave as high a yield as did 120 kg N/ha as urea applied without a green-manure crop. This suggests that the green manures tested added about 50% of the nitrogen needed by rice. ■

Green and dry matter production and nitrogen added by green manures in Ludhiana, India.^a

Green manure crop	Green matter (t/ha)	Dry matter (t/ha)	Nitrogen added (kg/ha)
Dhaincha	25	4.8	120
Cowpea	23	2.8	73
Guara	9	1.7	56

^aAverage of 3 years.

Grain yield (t/ha)

Effect of green manure plus nitrogen and nitrogen alone on yields in Ludhiana, India.